

**ON THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESTRICTED SEQUENCE OF
INTEGERS $2^{\omega(n)}$**

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Abstract

This paper studies the distribution of the sequence $2^{\omega(n)}$ over squareful integers n (we call an integer $n > 1$ squareful if for any prime p with $p|n$ implies $p^2|n$). We provide an unconditional asymptotic formula for the discrete mean sum of $2^{\omega(n)}$ over squareful integers. Additionally, assuming the Strong Riemann hypothesis, we extract a few more main terms, thereby improving the error term bound.

1. Introduction

Define $\omega(1) = 0$, and for $n > 1$, let $\omega(n)$ denote the number of distinct prime factors of n . We call an integer $n > 1$ squareful if for any prime p with $p|n$ implies $p^2|n$. Now, we define the arithmetical function $f(n)$ as $f(1) = 1$, and for $n > 1$,

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} 2^{\omega(n)} & \text{if } n \text{ is squareful,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Note that $f(n)$ is multiplicative. The L -function attached to the coefficients $f(n)$, namely

$$F(s) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{f(n)}{n^s}, \quad (1)$$

has the following Euler product

$$F(s) = \prod_p (1 + 2p^{-2s} + 2p^{-3s} + 2p^{-4s} + \dots) \quad (2)$$

for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$, and $F(s)$ converges absolutely and uniformly in $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$.

The Riemann zeta function is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s}$$

for $\Re(s) > 1$, which has a meromorphic continuation to the entire complex plane $\mathbb{C}$ by the functional equation

$$\zeta(s) = \chi(s)\zeta(1-s), \tag{3}$$

where the conversion factor $\chi(s)$ behaves, in absolute value, as

$$|\chi(s)| \sim |t|^{\frac{1}{2}-\sigma} \tag{4}$$

for $s = \sigma + it$, $|t| \geq t_0$ (see [4]).

The *Riemann hypothesis* is a conjecture that states that all the nontrivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ lie on the critical line $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{2}$. The *stronger version of the Riemann hypothesis* states that all the nontrivial zeros of $\zeta(s)$ lie on the critical line, and each such zero is simple. A region Ω is said to be a *zero-free region* for $\zeta(s)$ if $\zeta(s) \neq 0$ for all $s \in \Omega$. For the best-known zero-free region we refer to Theorem 6.1 of [1].

Throughout the paper, ϵ is any small positive constant. The aim here is to establish the following theorems.

Theorem 1. *Let $x > 0$ be large and $\epsilon > 0$. Then we have unconditionally,*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} f(n) = \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}} + \mathcal{C}_3 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_4 x^{\frac{1}{3}} + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{4}} \exp\left\{c\epsilon \left(\frac{\log x}{\log \log x}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}\right\}\right),$$

for some $c > 0$ and for real constants $\mathcal{C}_1$, $\mathcal{C}_2$, $\mathcal{C}_3$ and $\mathcal{C}_4$, that can be evaluated explicitly.

Theorem 2. *Let $x > 0$ be large and $\epsilon > 0$. Assuming the strong Riemann hypothesis namely, all the nontrivial zeros of $\zeta(ls)$ lie on the respective critical lines for $l = 2, 3, \dots, 14$, and each such zero is simple, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} f(n) &= \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}} + \mathcal{C}_3 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_4 x^{\frac{1}{3}} + \\ &+ \sum_{\substack{\zeta(4\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{8}, \\ 0 < \Im(4\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} x^{\frac{1}{8}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}} \\ &+ \sum_{\substack{\zeta(5\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{10}, \\ 0 < \Im(5\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \left(\mathcal{D}_2, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \log x + \mathcal{D}_3, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ \sum_{\substack{\zeta(6\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{12}, \\ 0 < \left| \Im(6\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} \right| < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \left(\mathcal{D}_4, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} (\log x)^2 \right. \\
 &+ \mathcal{D}_5, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} \log x + \mathcal{D}_6, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} \left. \right) + O\left(x^{\frac{5}{22}+\epsilon}\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

where C_i 's are certain real constants, and $\mathcal{D}_i$'s are certain complex constants that can be evaluated explicitly.

Remark 1. We observe that the main term

$$S_1 := \sum_{\substack{\zeta(4\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{8}, \\ 0 < \left| \Im(4\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} \right| < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} x^{\frac{1}{8}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}}$$

in Theorem 1, satisfies

$$|S_1| \leq x^{\frac{1}{8}} \left| \sum_{\substack{\zeta(4\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{8}, \\ 0 < \left| \Im(4\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} \right| < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} x^{i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}} \right|.$$

Since we expect enough cancellations to happen in the sum S_1 , we are tempted to make a plausible conjecture that $S_1 = O(x^{\frac{5}{22}+\epsilon})$, but we are not in a position to establish this assertion. It is also to be noted that, trivially,

$$|S_1| \leq x^{\frac{1}{8}} \left(\max_{\substack{\zeta(4\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{8}, \\ 0 < \left| \Im(4\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} \right| < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \left| \mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} \right| \right) T \log T \ll \left(\max_{\substack{\zeta(4\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{8}, \\ 0 < \left| \Im(4\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} \right| < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \left| \mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} \right| \right) x^{\frac{35}{88}+\epsilon}$$

with $T = x^{\frac{3}{11}}$. Observe that $\frac{1}{3} < \frac{35}{88}$. Similarly, we do expect cancellations to happen with the sums

$$S_2 := \sum_{\substack{\zeta(5\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{10}, \\ 0 < \left| \Im(5\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} \right| < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \left(\mathcal{D}_2, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \log x + \mathcal{D}_3, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \right)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_3 := &\sum_{\substack{\zeta(5\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{12}, \\ 0 < \left| \Im(6\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} \right| < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \left(\mathcal{D}_4, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} (\log x)^2 + \mathcal{D}_5, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} \log x \right. \\
 &\left. + \mathcal{D}_6, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

So conjecturally, we may have $S_2 = O(x^{\frac{5}{22}+\epsilon})$ and $S_3 = O(x^{\frac{5}{22}+\epsilon})$, but we are not in a position to prove them.

For further related problems of this type, interested readers may consult Chapter 14 of [1].

2. Lemmas

Lemma 1. For $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$, we have

$$F(s) = \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)\zeta^2(7s)\zeta^4(8s)\zeta^5(12s)\zeta^{14}(13s)\zeta^5(14s)}{\zeta(4s)\zeta^2(5s)\zeta^3(6s)\zeta^5(10s)\zeta^6(11s)}H_1(s), \tag{5}$$

where $H_1(s)$ is a Dirichlet series which converges absolutely and uniformly for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{15}$.

Proof. For $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$, we have the Euler product for $F(s)$ as

$$F(s) = \prod_p (1 + 2p^{-2s} + 2p^{-3s} + 2p^{-4s} + \dots). \tag{6}$$

If we let $X = p^{-s}$, then for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$, we have $|X| < 1$. To prove the lemma we split the series $1 + 2X^2 + 2X^3 + 2X^4 + \dots$ into the product of polynomials of the form $1 - X^m$ or its inverses from $m = 2$ to $m = 14$ possibly with some error terms.

By using the Mathematica software, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 + 2X^2 + 2X^3 + 2X^4 + 2X^5 + \dots \\ &= (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 + 2X^3 - X^4 - 2X^5) \\ &= (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} \times \\ &\quad (1 - X^4 - 2X^5 - 3X^6 + 2X^7 + 4X^8 + 2X^9 - X^{10} - 2X^{11}) \\ &= (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - 2X^5 - 3X^6 \\ &\quad + 2X^7 + 4X^8 - 4X^{10} + 4X^{12} - 4X^{14} + O(X^{15})) \\ &= (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - X^5)^2(1 - 3X^6 + 2X^7 \\ &\quad + 4X^8 - 5X^{10} - 6X^{11} + 8X^{12} + 8X^{13} - 4X^{14} + O(X^{15})) \\ &= (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - X^5)^2(1 - X^6)^3 \times \\ &\quad (1 + 2X^7 + 4X^8 - 5X^{10} - 6X^{11} + 5X^{12} + 14X^{13} + 8X^{14} + O(X^{15})) \\ &= (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - X^5)^2(1 - X^6)^3(1 - X^7)^{-2} \times \\ &\quad (1 + 4X^8 - 5X^{10} - 6X^{11} + 5X^{12} + 14X^{13} + 5X^{14} + O(X^{15})) \\ &= (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - X^5)^2(1 - X^6)^3(1 - X^7)^{-2}(1 - X^8)^{-4} \times \\ &\quad (1 - 5X^{10} - 6X^{11} + 5X^{12} + 14X^{13} + 5X^{14} + O(X^{15})) \\ &= (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - X^5)^2(1 - X^6)^3(1 - X^7)^{-2}(1 - X^8)^{-4} \times \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (1 - X^{10})^5(1 - 6X^{11} + 5X^{12} + 14X^{13} + 5X^{14} + O(X^{15})) \\
 = & (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - X^5)^2(1 - X^6)^3(1 - X^7)^{-2}(1 - X^8)^{-4} \times \\
 & (1 - X^{10})^5(1 - X^{11})^6(1 + 5X^{12} + 14X^{13} + 5X^{14} + O(X^{15})) \\
 = & (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - X^5)^2(1 - X^6)^3(1 - X^7)^{-2}(1 - X^8)^{-4} \times \\
 & (1 - X^{10})^5(1 - X^{11})^6(1 - X^{12})^{-5}(1 + 14X^{13} + 5X^{14} + O(X^{15})) \\
 = & (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - X^5)^2(1 - X^6)^3(1 - X^7)^{-2}(1 - X^8)^{-4} \times \\
 & (1 - X^{10})^5(1 - X^{11})^6(1 - X^{12})^{-5}(1 - X^{13})^{-14}(1 + 5X^{14} + O(X^{15})) \\
 = & (1 - X^2)^{-2} (1 - X^3)^{-2} (1 - X^4)(1 - X^5)^2(1 - X^6)^3(1 - X^7)^{-2}(1 - X^8)^{-4} \times \\
 & (1 - X^{10})^5(1 - X^{11})^6(1 - X^{12})^{-5}(1 - X^{13})^{-14}(1 - X^{14})^{-5}(1 + O(X^{15})). \quad (7)
 \end{aligned}$$

By substituting $X = p^{-s}$ in the above expression, by (6) we then get

$$F(s) = \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)\zeta^2(7s)\zeta^4(8s)\zeta^5(12s)\zeta^{14}(13s)\zeta^5(14s)}{\zeta(4s)\zeta^2(5s)\zeta^3(6s)\zeta^5(10s)\zeta^6(11s)} H_1(s),$$

where $H_1(s)$ converges absolutely and uniformly for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{15}$. □

Lemma 2. For $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$, we have

$$F(s) = \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)}{\zeta(4s)} H_2(s), \tag{8}$$

where $H_2(s)$ converges absolutely and uniformly for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{5}$.

Proof. From Lemma 1, we can write

$$F(s) = \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)}{\zeta(4s)} H_2(s),$$

where

$$H_2(s) = \frac{\zeta^2(7s)\zeta^4(8s)\zeta^5(12s)\zeta^{14}(13s)\zeta^5(14s)}{\zeta^2(5s)\zeta^3(6s)\zeta^5(10s)\zeta^6(11s)} H_1(s),$$

which converges absolutely and uniformly for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{5}$. □

Remark 2. In the proofs of Theorems 1 and 2, we use either Lemma 1 or Lemma 2 suitably.

Lemma 3. Let $x > 0$ be large. Then under the assumption of the strong Riemann hypothesis for various zeta functions $\zeta(ls)$ appearing in $F(s)$ proved in Lemma 1 ($l = 2, 3, 4, \dots, 14$), we have the following residues corresponding to the poles arising from $F(s)$:

$$\operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{2}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} = \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}}, \tag{9}$$

$$\operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{3}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} = \mathcal{C}_3 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_4 x^{\frac{1}{3}}, \tag{10}$$

$$\operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{7}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} = \mathcal{C}_5 x^{\frac{1}{7}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_6 x^{\frac{1}{7}}, \tag{11}$$

$$\operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{8}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} = \mathcal{C}_7 x^{\frac{1}{8}} (\log x)^3 + \mathcal{C}_8 x^{\frac{1}{8}} (\log x)^2 + \mathcal{C}_9 x^{\frac{1}{8}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_{10} x^{\frac{1}{8}}, \tag{12}$$

$$\operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{12}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} = \mathcal{C}_{11} x^{\frac{1}{12}} (\log x)^4 + \dots + \mathcal{C}_{14} x^{\frac{1}{12}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_{15} x^{\frac{1}{12}}, \tag{13}$$

$$\operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{13}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} = \mathcal{C}_{16} x^{\frac{1}{13}} (\log x)^{13} + \dots + \mathcal{C}_{28} x^{\frac{1}{13}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_{29} x^{\frac{1}{13}}, \tag{14}$$

$$\operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{8}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} = \mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} x^{\frac{1}{8}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}}, \tag{15}$$

$$\operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} = \mathcal{D}_2, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \log x + \mathcal{D}_3, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}}, \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} &= \mathcal{D}_4, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} (\log x)^2 + \mathcal{D}_5, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} \log x \\ &+ \mathcal{D}_6, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}}, \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

where $\frac{1}{8} + \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}$, $\frac{1}{10} + \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}$ and $\frac{1}{12} + \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}$ are the coordinates of the simple zeros of $\zeta(4s)$, $\zeta(5s)$ and $\zeta(6s)$ on the lines $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{8}$, $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{10}$ and $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{12}$ respectively, and the $\mathcal{C}_i$'s, and $\mathcal{D}_i$'s are constants that can be evaluated explicitly.

Proof. By Lemma 1, for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$, we have

$$F(s) = \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)\zeta^2(7s)\zeta^4(8s)\zeta^5(12s)\zeta^{14}(13s)\zeta^5(14s)}{\zeta(4s)\zeta^2(5s)\zeta^3(6s)\zeta^5(10s)\zeta^6(11s)} H_1(s), \tag{18}$$

where $H_1(s)$ converges absolutely and uniformly for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{15}$.

Let

$$F_1(s) := \frac{\zeta^2(3s)\zeta^2(7s)\zeta^4(8s)\zeta^5(12s)\zeta^{14}(13s)\zeta^5(14s)}{\zeta(4s)\zeta^2(5s)\zeta^3(6s)\zeta^5(10s)\zeta^6(11s)} H_1(s), \tag{19}$$

which is analytic at $s = \frac{1}{2}$, and hence, $F(s) = \zeta^2(2s)F_1(s)$ has a pole of order 2 at $s = \frac{1}{2}$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{2}} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} &= \left(F_1(s) \frac{x^s}{s} \right)' \Big|_{s=\frac{1}{2}} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{2}} \left(s - \frac{1}{2} \right) \zeta^2(2s) + F_1 \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) \frac{x^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\frac{1}{2}} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{2}} \zeta^2(2s) \\ &:= \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{C}_1$ and $\mathcal{C}_2$ are some constants that can be evaluated explicitly. Similarly, the equalities from (10) to (14) can be proved.

Now, for any simple zero $\frac{1}{8} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}$ of $\zeta(4s)$ lying on the critical line $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{8}$, we have that

$$F_2(s) := \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)\zeta^2(7s)\zeta^4(8s)\zeta^5(12s)\zeta^{14}(13s)\zeta^5(14s)}{\zeta^2(5s)\zeta^3(6s)\zeta^5(10s)\zeta^6(11s)}H_1(s) \tag{20}$$

is analytic at $s = \frac{1}{8} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}$ and hence, $F(s) = \frac{F_2(s)}{\zeta(4s)}$ has a simple pole at $\frac{1}{8} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{8}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}} F(s)\frac{x^s}{s} &= F_2\left(\frac{1}{8} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}\right) \frac{x^{\frac{1}{8}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}}}{\frac{1}{8} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{8}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}} \frac{1}{\zeta(4s)} \\ &:= \mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} x^{\frac{1}{8}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}$ is some constant which can be evaluated explicitly.

Similarly, for any simple zero $\frac{1}{10} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}$ of $\zeta(5s)$ lying on the critical line $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{10}$, we have that

$$F_3(s) := \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)\zeta^2(7s)\zeta^4(8s)\zeta^5(12s)\zeta^{14}(13s)\zeta^5(14s)}{\zeta(4s)\zeta^3(6s)\zeta^5(10s)\zeta^6(11s)}H_1(s) \tag{21}$$

is analytic at $s = \frac{1}{10} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}$ and hence, $F(s) = \frac{F_3(s)}{\zeta^2(5s)}$ has a pole of order 2 at $\frac{1}{10} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} F(s)\frac{x^s}{s} &= \left(F_3(s)\frac{x^s}{s}\right)'_{s=\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \left(s - \frac{1}{10} - i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}\right) \frac{1}{\zeta^2(5s)} \\ &\quad + F_3\left(\frac{1}{10} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}\right) \frac{x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}}}{\frac{1}{10} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \frac{1}{\zeta^2(5s)} \\ &:= \mathcal{D}_2, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \log x + \mathcal{D}_3, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{D}_2, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}$ and $\mathcal{D}_3, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}$ are some constants that can be evaluated explicitly.

Similarly, the equality (17) can be proved. This completes the proof of this lemma. $\square$

Lemma 4 ([4, 5]). *For any $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1$, and T -sufficiently large, we have*

$$\int_1^T |\zeta(\sigma + it)|^4 dt \ll T(\log T)^4 \tag{22}$$

uniformly.

Lemma 5 ([1]). *There is a constant $C > 0$ such that*

$$\frac{1}{\zeta(s)} \ll (\log T)^{2/3}(\log \log T)^{1/3} \tag{23}$$

in the region $\sigma \geq 1 - \frac{C}{(\log T)^{2/3}(\log \log T)^{1/3}}$, $T_0 < t \leq T$.

Lemma 6 ([1]). *There is a constant $C^* > 0$ such that $\zeta(s) \neq 0$ for $\sigma \geq 1 - \frac{C^*}{(\log T)^{2/3}(\log \log T)^{1/3}}$, $|t| \geq t_0$.*

Lemma 7 ([1, 3]). *We have $N(T) \ll T \log T$, where $N(T)$ is the number of zeros of $\zeta(s)$ in the region $\{s = \sigma + it : 0 < \sigma < 1, 0 < t \leq T\}$.*

Lemma 8 ([4]). *The Riemann hypothesis implies that*

$$\zeta(\sigma + it) = O(|t|^\epsilon) \tag{24}$$

for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1$ and $|t| \geq t_0$, and

$$\frac{1}{\zeta(\sigma + it)} = O(|t|^\epsilon) \tag{25}$$

for $\frac{1}{2} < \sigma \leq 1$ and $|t| \geq t_0$.

3. Proof of Theorem 1

We are now ready to prove Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. By Lemma 2, for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$, we have

$$F(s) = \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)}{\zeta(4s)}H_2(s), \tag{26}$$

where $H_2(s)$ converges absolutely and uniformly for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{5}$.

By applying Perron’s formula (see [2]) to Equation (26), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} f(n) &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \text{ is squareful}}} 2^{\omega(n)} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} - iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}}(\log x)^2}{T}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $1 \leq T \leq x$ is a parameter to be chosen later.

We move the line of integration to $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{(\log T)^{2/3}(\log \log T)^{1/3}}$, where $c = C^*$ as in Lemma 6. Define $g(T) := (\log T)^{2/3}(\log \log T)^{1/3}$. Then, in the rectangle formed by the vertices $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT$, $\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)} + iT$, $\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)} - iT$, $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} - iT$, and $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT$, we note that $F(s)$ has two poles, one at $s = \frac{1}{2}$ of order 2 and another at $s = \frac{1}{3}$ of order 2.

Hence, by Cauchy’s residue theorem and Lemma 3, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} f(n) &= \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}} + \mathcal{C}_3 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_4 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left\{ \int_{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)} - iT}^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)} + iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} - iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)} + iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT} \right\} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} (\log x)^2}{T}\right) \\ &:= \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}} + \mathcal{C}_3 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_4 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \\ &\quad + I_1 + I_2 + I_3 + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} (\log x)^2}{T}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

The vertical line integration I_1 contributes in absolute value (by using the functional equation (Equation (3)) for $\zeta(s)$, the approximation (Equation (4)) for $\chi(s)$, and Lemmas 4 and 5):

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &\ll \int_{-T}^T \left| \frac{\zeta^2\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{2c}{g(T)} + 2it\right) \zeta^2\left(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3c}{g(T)} + 3it\right)}{\zeta\left(1 - \frac{4c}{g(T)} + 4it\right)} \right| \frac{x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}}}{t} dt \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} + x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} \int_{10}^T \left| \frac{\zeta^2\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{2c}{g(T)} + 2it\right) \zeta^2\left(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3c}{g(T)} + 3it\right)}{\zeta\left(1 - \frac{4c}{g(T)} + 4it\right) t} \right| dt \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} + x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} g(T) \times \\ &\quad \int_{10}^T \left| \zeta^2\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{2c}{g(T)} + 2it\right) \zeta^2\left(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3c}{g(T)} + 3it\right) \right| t^{-1} dt \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} + x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} g(T) T^{2\left(\frac{1}{2} - \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{2c}{g(T)}\right)\right)} \times \\ &\quad \int_{10}^T \left| \zeta^2\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2c}{g(T)} - 2it\right) \zeta^2\left(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3c}{g(T)} + 3it\right) \right| t^{-1} dt \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} + x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} g(T) \exp\left\{4c \frac{\log T}{g(T)}\right\} \times \\ &\quad \sup_{10 \leq T_1 \leq T} \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2c}{g(T)} - 2it\right) \right|^4 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \times \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \zeta^2 \left(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3c}{g(T)} + 3it \right) \right|^4 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} T_1^{-1} \\
 & \ll x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} + x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} (\log T)^{2/3} (\log \log T)^{1/3} \times \\
 & \quad \exp \left\{ 4c \left(\frac{\log T}{\log \log T} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \right\} T (\log T)^4 T^{-1} \\
 & \ll x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} (\log \log T)^{1/3} (\log T)^{\frac{14}{3}} \exp \left\{ 4c \left(\frac{\log T}{\log \log T} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \right\} \\
 & \ll x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} \exp \left\{ (4 + \epsilon)c \left(\frac{\log T}{\log \log T} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \right\} \tag{28}
 \end{aligned}$$

for some small $\epsilon > 0$.

The horizontal line portions I_2 and I_3 contribute in absolute value (by using the functional equation (Equation (3)) for $\zeta(s)$, the approximation (Equation (4)) for $\chi(s)$, and Lemma 5) a total of

$$\begin{aligned}
 |I_2| + |I_3| & \leq 10 \int_{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)} + iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT} \left| \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)}{\zeta(4s)} \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\
 & \ll \frac{g(T)}{T} \int_{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)} + iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT} |\chi^2(2s)\zeta^2(1-2s)\zeta^2(1-3s)x^s ds| \\
 & \ll \frac{g(T)}{T} \int_{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} T^{2(\frac{1}{2}-2\sigma)} T^{\frac{2}{3}(1-(1-2\sigma)) + \frac{2}{3}(1-3\sigma)} x^\sigma d\sigma \\
 & \ll \frac{g(T)}{T} \int_{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} T^{\frac{5}{3} - \frac{14\sigma}{3}} x^\sigma d\sigma \\
 & \ll g(T) T^{\frac{2}{3}} \int_{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} \left(\frac{x}{T^{\frac{14}{3}}} \right)^\sigma d\sigma \\
 & \ll (\log T)^{2/3} (\log \log T)^{1/3} T^{\frac{2}{3}} \left\{ x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} T^{-\frac{7}{3} - \frac{14}{3} \frac{1}{\log x}} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{(\log T)^{2/3} (\log \log T)^{1/3}}} T^{-\frac{7}{6} + \frac{14}{3} \frac{c}{(\log T)^{2/3} (\log \log T)^{1/3}}} \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that, for $T \gg x^{\frac{1}{4}}$, we have

$$|I_2| + |I_3| \ll x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{(\log T)^{2/3} (\log \log T)^{1/3}}} T^{-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{14}{3} \frac{c}{(\log T)^{2/3} (\log \log T)^{1/3}}} (\log T)^{2/3} (\log \log T)^{1/3}. \tag{29}$$

Therefore, for $T \gg x^{\frac{1}{4}}$, from Equations (27), (28), and (29), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} f(n) &= \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}} + \mathcal{C}_3 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_4 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \\ &+ O\left(x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{c}{g(T)}} \exp\left\{(4 + \epsilon)c \left(\frac{\log T}{\log \log T}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}\right\}\right) + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} (\log x)^2}{T}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Finally, by making our choice $T = x^{\frac{1}{4}} (\log x)^2 \exp\left\{-c\epsilon \left(\frac{\log x}{\log \log x}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}\right\}$, we obtain

$$\sum_{n \leq x} f(n) = \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}} + \mathcal{C}_3 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_4 x^{\frac{1}{3}} + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{4}} \exp\left\{c\epsilon \left(\frac{\log x}{\log \log x}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}\right\}\right),$$

for some real constants $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \mathcal{C}_3, \mathcal{C}_4$ that can be evaluated explicitly. This proves Theorem 1. $\square$

4. Proof of Theorem 2

Proof of Theorem 2. By Lemma 1, for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$, we have

$$F(s) = \frac{\zeta^2(2s)\zeta^2(3s)\zeta^2(7s)\zeta^4(8s)\zeta^5(12s)\zeta^{14}(13s)\zeta^5(14s)}{\zeta(4s)\zeta^2(5s)\zeta^3(6s)\zeta^5(10s)\zeta^6(11s)} H_1(s), \tag{31}$$

where $H_1(s)$ converges absolutely and uniformly for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{15}$.

By applying Perron’s formula (see [2]) to Equation (31), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \text{ is squareful}}} f(n) &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \text{ is squareful}}} 2^{\omega(n)} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} - iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} (\log x)^2}{T}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $1 \leq T \leq x$ is a parameter to be chosen later.

Here, we move the line of integration to $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}$. Then, in the rectangle $\mathcal{R}$ formed by the vertices $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT, \frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT, \frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} - iT, \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} - iT$, and $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT$, we note that $F(s)$ has poles at the points $s = \frac{1}{2}$ of order 2, $s = \frac{1}{3}$ of order 2, $s = \frac{1}{7}$ of order 2, $s = \frac{1}{8}$ of order 4, $s = \frac{1}{12}$ of order 5, $s = \frac{1}{13}$ of order 14, a simple pole at each $s = \frac{1}{8} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}$, a pole of order 2 at each $s = \frac{1}{10} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}$ and a pole of order 3 at each $s = \frac{1}{12} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}$, where $\frac{1}{8} + \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}, \frac{1}{10} + \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}$ and $\frac{1}{12} + \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}$ are the coordinates of the zeros of $\zeta(4s), \zeta(5s)$

and $\zeta(6s)$ on the lines $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{8}$, $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{10}$ and $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{12}$ respectively, such that $|\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}|, |\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}|, |\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}| < T$.

Hence, by Cauchy’s residue theorem, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} f(n) &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left\{ \int_{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} - iT}^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} - iT}^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} - iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT} \right\} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \\ &\quad + \sum_{\rho} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\rho} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} (\log x)^2}{T}\right) \\ &:= J_1 + J_2 + J_3 + \sum_{\rho} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\rho} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} (\log x)^2}{T}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

where in the right-hand side sum, ρ runs over all the poles of $F(s)$ inside the rectangle $\mathcal{R}$.

The vertical line integration J_1 contributes in absolute value (by using the functional equation (Equation (3)) for $\zeta(s)$, the approximation (Equation (4)) for $\chi(s)$, and Equations (24) and (25)):

$$\begin{aligned} J_1 &\ll \left| \int_{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} - iT}^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} \\ &\quad + \int_{10}^T \left| \frac{\zeta^2\left(\frac{1}{7} + \frac{2}{\log x} + 2it\right) \zeta^2\left(\frac{3}{14} + \frac{3}{\log x} + 3it\right) x^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} t^{-1+41\epsilon}}{\zeta\left(\frac{2}{7} + \frac{4}{\log x} + 4it\right) \zeta^2\left(\frac{5}{14} + \frac{5}{\log x} + 5it\right) \zeta^3\left(\frac{3}{7} + \frac{6}{\log x} + 6it\right)} \right| dt \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} + x^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{2\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{7} - \frac{2}{\log \log x}\right) + 2\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{14} - \frac{3}{\log \log x}\right)} \times \\ &\quad T^{-\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{2}{7} - \frac{4}{\log \log x}\right) - 2\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{5}{14} - \frac{5}{\log \log x}\right) - 3\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{7} - \frac{6}{\log \log x}\right)} \times \\ &\quad \int_{10}^T \left| \frac{\zeta^2\left(\frac{6}{7} - \frac{2}{\log x} - 2it\right) \zeta^2\left(\frac{11}{14} - \frac{3}{\log x} - 3it\right) t^{-1+41\epsilon}}{\zeta\left(\frac{5}{7} - \frac{4}{\log x} - 4it\right) \zeta^2\left(\frac{9}{14} - \frac{5}{\log x} - 5it\right) \zeta^3\left(\frac{4}{7} - \frac{6}{\log x} - 6it\right)} \right| dt \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} + x^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{\frac{4}{7} + \frac{22}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon} (\log T) \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{\frac{4}{7} + \frac{22}{\log \log x} + 52\epsilon}. \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Now, to find the contributions coming from the horizontal line portions J_2 and J_3 in absolute value, (to see more clearly) we divide the interval $\left[\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}, \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}\right]$ into the union of the following six intervals: $\left[\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}, \frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}\right]$, $\left[\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}, \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}\right]$, $\left[\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}, \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}\right]$, $\left[\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}, \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}\right]$, $\left[\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}, \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}\right]$ and $\left[\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}, \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}\right]$. Then, by using the functional equation (Equation (3)) for $\zeta(s)$, the approximation (Equation (4)) for $\chi(s)$,

and Equations (24) and (25), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 |J_2| + |J_3| &\leq 10 \left| \int_{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\
 &\ll \left\{ \int_{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT}^{\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT}^{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT}^{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT}^{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT}^{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} + iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT} \right\} \times \\
 &\quad \left| \frac{\zeta^2(2\sigma + 2iT)\zeta^2(3\sigma + 3iT)}{\zeta(4\sigma + 4iT)\zeta^2(5\sigma + 5iT)\zeta^3(6\sigma + 6iT)} \right| x^\sigma T^{-1+41\epsilon} d\sigma \\
 &\ll \max_{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{2(1-5\sigma) - (\frac{1}{2}-4\sigma) - 2(\frac{1}{2}-5\sigma) - 3(\frac{1}{2}-6\sigma) - 1 + 51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{2(1-5\sigma) - (\frac{1}{2}-4\sigma) - 2(\frac{1}{2}-5\sigma) - 1 + 51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{2(1-5\sigma) - (\frac{1}{2}-4\sigma) - 1 + 51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{2(1-5\sigma) - 1 + 51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{2(\frac{1}{2}-2\sigma) - 1 + 51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} x^\sigma T^{-1+51\epsilon} \\
 &\ll \max_{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{-2+22\sigma+51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{-\frac{1}{2}+4\sigma+51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{\frac{1}{2}-6\sigma+51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{1-10\sigma+51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} x^\sigma T^{-4\sigma+51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + \max_{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} \leq \sigma \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} x^\sigma T^{-1+51\epsilon} \\
 &\ll x^{\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{-2 + \frac{22}{12} + \frac{22}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon} + x^{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{4}{10} + \frac{4}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + x^{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{6}{10} - \frac{6}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon} + x^{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{6}{8} - \frac{6}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + x^{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{1 - \frac{10}{8} - \frac{10}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon} + x^{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{1 - \frac{10}{6} - \frac{10}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + x^{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{-\frac{4}{6} - \frac{4}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon} + x^{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x}} T^{-\frac{4}{4} - \frac{4}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x}} T^{-1+51\epsilon} \\
 \ll &x^{\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{1}{6} + \frac{22}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} + x^{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{1}{10} + \frac{4}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} \\
 &+ x^{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{1}{10} - \frac{6}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} + x^{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{1}{4} - \frac{6}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} \\
 &+ x^{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{1}{4} - \frac{10}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} + x^{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{2}{3} - \frac{10}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} \\
 &+ x^{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{2}{3} - \frac{4}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} + x^{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-1 - \frac{4}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} \\
 &+ x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} T^{-1+51\epsilon}} \\
 \ll &x^{\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{1}{6} + \frac{22}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} + x^{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{1}{10} + \frac{4}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} \\
 &+ x^{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{1}{4} - \frac{6}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} + x^{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{-\frac{2}{3} - \frac{4}{\log \log x} + 51\epsilon}} \\
 &+ x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} T^{-1+51\epsilon}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that, for $T \gg x^{\frac{1}{4}}$, we have

$$|J_2| + |J_3| \ll x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} T^{-1+51\epsilon}}. \tag{34}$$

Therefore, for $T \gg x^{\frac{1}{4}}$, from Equations (32), (33), (34), and Lemma 3, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n \leq x} f(n) = & \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}} + \mathcal{C}_3 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_4 x^{\frac{1}{3}} + \mathcal{C}_5 x^{\frac{1}{7}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_6 x^{\frac{1}{7}} \\
 &+ \mathcal{C}_7 x^{\frac{1}{8}} (\log x)^3 + \mathcal{C}_8 x^{\frac{1}{8}} (\log x)^2 + \mathcal{C}_9 x^{\frac{1}{8}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_{10} x^{\frac{1}{8}} \\
 &+ \mathcal{C}_{11} x^{\frac{1}{12}} (\log x)^4 + \dots + \mathcal{C}_{14} x^{\frac{1}{12}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_{15} x^{\frac{1}{12}} \\
 &+ \mathcal{C}_{16} x^{\frac{1}{13}} (\log x)^{13} + \dots + \mathcal{C}_{28} x^{\frac{1}{13}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_{29} x^{\frac{1}{13}} \\
 &+ \sum_{\substack{\zeta(4\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{8}, \\ 0 < \Im(4\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} < T}} \mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} x^{\frac{1}{8} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}} \\
 &+ \sum_{\substack{\zeta(5\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{10}, \\ 0 < \Im(5\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} < T}} \left(\mathcal{D}_2, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \log x + \mathcal{D}_3, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \right) \\
 &+ \sum_{\substack{\zeta(6\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{12}, \\ 0 < \Im(6\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} < T}} \left(\mathcal{D}_4, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} (\log x)^2 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \mathcal{D}_5, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} \log x + \mathcal{D}_6, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12} + i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} \right) \\
 &+ O\left(x^{\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{\log \log x} T^{\frac{4}{7} + \frac{22}{\log \log x} + 52\epsilon}}\right) + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\log x} T^{-1+51\epsilon}}\right). \tag{35}
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, by making our choice $T = x^{\frac{3}{11}}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} f(n) = & \mathcal{C}_1 x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_2 x^{\frac{1}{2}} + \mathcal{C}_3 x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + \mathcal{C}_4 x^{\frac{1}{3}} + \\ & + \sum_{\substack{\zeta(4\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{8}, \\ 0 < \Im(4\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \mathcal{D}_1, \gamma_{\frac{1}{8}} x^{\frac{1}{8}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{8}}} \\ & + \sum_{\substack{\zeta(5\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{10}, \\ 0 < \Im(5\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \left(\mathcal{D}_2, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \log x + \mathcal{D}_3, \gamma_{\frac{1}{10}} x^{\frac{1}{10}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{10}}} \right) \\ & + \sum_{\substack{\zeta(6\rho)=0, \Re(\rho)=\frac{1}{12}, \\ 0 < \Im(6\rho)=\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} < x^{\frac{3}{11}}}} \left(\mathcal{D}_4, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} (\log x)^2 \right. \\ & \left. + \mathcal{D}_5, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} \log x + \mathcal{D}_6, \gamma_{\frac{1}{12}} x^{\frac{1}{12}+i\gamma_{\frac{1}{12}}} \right) + O\left(x^{\frac{5}{22}+\epsilon}\right). \end{aligned}$$

This proves Theorem 2. □

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